
Scalable full-cycle marine litter remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and participatory solutions

SeaClear2.0

<https://www.seaclear2.eu>

D6.2

Dissemination Resources

WP6 – Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination

Grant Agreement no. 101093822

Lead beneficiary: ISOTECH Ltd

Date: 28/06/2023

Type: R

Dissemination level: PU

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Document information

Grant agreement no.	101093822
Acronym:	SeaClear2.0
Full title:	Scalable full-cycle marine litter remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and participatory solutions
Start date of the project	01/01/2023
Duration of the project	48 months
Deliverable	D6.2: Dissemination Resources
Work package	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination
Deliverable leader	ISOTECH Ltd
Delivery date	Contractual: 30/06/2023 Actual: 28/06/2023
Status	Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Type¹	R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DEM <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER <input type="checkbox"/> DMP <input type="checkbox"/>
Dissemination level²	PU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> C-UE/EU-C <input type="checkbox"/> SEN <input type="checkbox"/>
Author(s)	Demetra Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd) Demetra Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)
Responsible author	Demetra Kallitsi, email: network@isotech.com.cy ISOTECH Ltd
Deliverable description	This report will contain the communication and dissemination resources that will be developed for the project, e.g. project logo and tagline, presentation and poster templates, project website, and social media accounts. (<=T6.2)

¹ R = Document, report, DEM = Demonstrator, OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc., DMP = Data Management Plan

² PU = Public, C-UE/EU-C = EU Confidential under Decision 2015/444, SEN = Sensitive

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Document history

Name	Date	Version	Description
D. Kallitsi & D. Orthodoxou	31/05/2023	V1.0	First draft submitted to reviewers
D. Kallitsi & D. Orthodoxou	27/06/2023	V1.1	Final version with comments from reviewers (W. Murtinu-van Schagen, B. De Schutter, L. Busoniu)

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Disclaimer of Warranties

This document has been prepared by SeaClear2.0 project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of Grant Agreement no. 101093822. Neither the Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of the SeaClear2.0 Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

- makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express or implied, with respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose, that such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property; or
- makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express or implied, that this document is suitable to any particular user's circumstance; or
- assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever (including any consequential damages, even if the Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the Project Consortium Agreement, has been advised of the possibility of such damages) resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. SeaClear2.0 Visual Identity and Brand.....	8
2.1 Project Logo	8
2.2 Project Colour Palette	10
2.3 Project Typeface.....	11
3. SeaClear2.0 Templates.....	12
3.1 Project Deliverable Template	12
3.2 PowerPoint Presentation Template.....	12
3.3 Poster Template for Events.....	15
3.4 Project Poster.....	16
3.5 Project Roll-up Banner	17
4. Communication Tools	19
4.1 Project Website.....	19
4.2 Social Media Channels	19
4.3 SeaClear2.0 Zenodo Community	20
4.4 SeaClear2.0 Introductory Presentation	20
4.5 Animation Video	21
5. Communication and Dissemination Guidelines	22
5.1 Project Information on Institutional Websites and Social Media.....	22
5.2 Project Poster Display	22
5.3 Acknowledgement of EU Funding.....	22
5.4 Scientific Publications and Data	24
5.5 Press Articles	24
5.6 Social Media Posts	24
5.7 Continuous Reporting of Communication and Dissemination Activities	25
6. Conclusions	26

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Definitions

- **Beneficiary:** A legal entity that is signatory of the EC Grant Agreement no. 101093822.
- **Consortium:** The SeaClear2.0 Consortium, comprising the list of beneficiaries below.
- **Consortium Agreement:** Agreement concluded amongst the SeaClear2.0 beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement.
- **Grant Agreement:** The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the SeaClear2.0 project (Grant Agreement no. 101093822).

Beneficiaries of the SeaClear2.0 Consortium are referred to herein according to the following abbreviations:

- **TU Delft:** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
- **DUNEA:** REGIONALNA AGENCIJA DUNEA
- **Fraunhofer:** FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV
- **HPA:** HAMBURG PORT AUTHORITY
- **ISOTECH:** ISOTECH LTD
- **MDanchor:** M. DANCHOR LTD
- **Subsea Tech:** SUBSEA TECH SAS
- **TECNOSUB:** TÉCNICAS Y OBRAS SUBACUÁTICAS, SLU
- **TUM:** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN
- **UNIDU:** SVEUCILISTE U DUBROVNIKU
- **UTC:** UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA CLUJ-NAPOCA
- **VEO:** VEOLIA PROPRETE
- **VLPF:** VENICE LAGOON PLASTIC FREE

Abbreviations

- **EC:** European Commission
- **GA:** Grant Agreement
- **WP:** Work Package

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Executive Summary

This report, Deliverable 6.2 “Dissemination Resources”, is the second deliverable of Work Package 6 of the SeaClear2.0 project, which deals with public engagement, policy and dissemination. It is complementary to D6.1 ‘Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan’ as it presents the main communication resources developed for the project.

The report begins with a brief introduction (Chapter 1), and moves on to present the visual identity and brand of SeaClear2.0 (Chapter 2), the communication templates (Chapter 3) and the communication tools/channels (Chapter 4) developed. The last part of the report (Chapter 5) acts as a short communication and dissemination guide for the partners.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

1. Introduction

The SeaClear2.0 project aims to develop and demonstrate a new paradigm for marine litter prevention and reduction, through a combination of technological innovations, policy-making, and community activation. Communication and dissemination activities are an integral part of SeaClear2.0 since they play a pivotal role in effectively transferring key messages about the project, including project activities and results, to target audiences.

There are two interconnected aspects to communication and dissemination. The first is the development of the strategy and plan for communication and dissemination, which is presented in D6.1 “Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan”. The second aspect is the subject of this deliverable and concerns the development of the communication and dissemination resources that will ensure that the project has a strong visual identity and online presence.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

2. SeaClear2.0 Visual Identity and Brand

This chapter presents the visual identity and brand of the SeaClear2.0 project through the project logo, colours, and typeface used.

2.1 Project Logo

The project logo is a key part of the project brand and is included in all project templates and promotional material (Figure 1). The logo was developed at project proposal stage and refined at the beginning of the project. The logo contains key elements that allude to the objectives of the project. It is a circular logo, alluding to the circular economy and the rounded approach taken by SeaClear2.0 to address the issue of marine litter. The wave is a key element of the logo, as are the hues of blue colour, emphasising the marine nature of the project. The word “SeaClear” and the number “2.0” are located at a slight distance and with a height differential. While the emphasis is on the “2.0”, the separation of the two elements helps to create the link with the SeaClear project.

Figure 1 SeaClear2.0 project logo in colour (left) and monochrome (right)

A black and white version of the logo has also been developed. The black and white logo is only intended for project materials developed on a black and white colour scale (e.g., black and white printing). Both logos are available on the SeaClear2.0 shared drive and can be requested from the WP6 leader, ISOTECH (network@isotech.com.cy).

2.1.1 Correct use of the logo

The designated background colour when using the project logo is white. For project materials that use a different background colour (e.g., leaflet, photo), please make sure that the logo can still be depicted clearly. For further information, please refer to the examples below:

Incorrect: The coloured logo is not fully visible on the darker background.

Incorrect: The black and white logo is not clearly visible on the darker background.

Correct: the coloured version of the logo is fully and clearly visible against the lighter background.

Correct: the black and white version of the logo is fully and clearly visible against the lighter background.

For project materials that use images as a background colour (e.g., leaflet, photo) please make sure that the logo can still be depicted clearly. For further information, please refer to the examples below:

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Incorrect: The coloured logo is not fully visible on the darker background.

Correct: the coloured version of the logo is fully and clearly visible against the background

Please do not:

- modify, add, or rearrange elements of the logo
- use stand-alone elements of the logo
- modify logo colours
- distort the logo

2.2 Project Colour Palette

The designated colour palette to be used in SeaClear2.0 project materials is given below.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

2.3 Project Typeface

The primary typeface selected for SeaClear2.0 project materials is Calibri. Please use it in Regular or **Bold** only. Calibri is available or can be freely downloaded for used on in all Microsoft, Mac and Linux computers.

Calibri
ABCDEFGHIJKLMN**OP**QRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwx**yz**
0123456789 @*?!&%+=''

Calibri Bold
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOP**QRSTUVWXYZ**
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz****
0123456789 @*?!&%+=''

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

3. SeaClear2.0 Templates

The templates that have been developed for use by the project partnerships are presented in this chapter. All the templates are available on the SeaClear2.0 shared drive and can be requested from the WP6 leader, ISOTECH (network@isotech.com.cy).

3.1 Project Deliverable Template

The project deliverable template has been developed by the project coordinator, TU Delft. It is available on the SeaClear2.0 shared drive. It is used for all deliverables, including this one.

3.2 PowerPoint Presentation Template

A SeaClear2.0 PowerPoint template has been developed to be used at both internal and external events when presenting the project. The template includes:

- A cover slide (Figure 2): this includes the logo of the project on the top right and a placeholder for the logo of the presenting partner on the top left. Placeholders for the title of the presentation, the event where the presentation is given, and the name of the author are available. The project website is also visible on the cover slide.
- Two main body slides (Figure 3): this is where the main body of the presentation can go. One slide contains the graphical explanation of the SeaClear2.0 system, whereas the other one is a much simpler one, with ample space for inputting text and/or figures.
- A thank you/closing slide (Figure 4): this includes contact details for the project coordinator and the project communication lead, and placeholders for contact information of the presenter. A LinkTree QR code is available on the closing slide. When this is scanned, users are taken to a page from where they can subscribe to all (or a selection) of the project's social media, newsletters etc. (Figure 5).

The EU logo and disclaimer appear in all PowerPoint slides.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Insert your logo here

Title of presentation

Event and date

www.seaclear2.eu

[Presenter's name and info here]

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Slide 1

Figure 2 SeaClear2.0 PowerPoint presentation template cover slide

Click to add title

- Click to add text

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Slide 3

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Click to add title

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Slide 4

Figure 3 SeaClear2.0 presentation template main body slides

Insert your logo here

Thank you

Name: *[Project partner's name here]*

Affiliation: *[Project partner's affiliation here]*

Email: *[Project partner's contact email here]*

Website: *[Project partner's website here]*

Social Media: *[Project partner's handle 1 here]*

Social Media: *[Project partner's handle 2 here]*

Project coordinator:
Dr. Bart De Schutter
 TU Delft
b.deschutter@tudelft.nl

Project communications lead:
 Ms. Demetra Kallitsi
 ISOTECH Ltd
network@isotech.com.cy

Follow us

www.seaclear2.eu

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Slide 5

Figure 4 SeaClear2.0 presentation template thank you/closing slide

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Figure 5 LinkTree QR code landing page

3.3 Poster Template for Events

A poster template has been developed to be used by partners during conference/exhibition poster sessions. The poster template resembles the presentation template in terms of graphical elements and colours used. It is quite simple in nature, to allow for input of text and figures as needed. It includes basic, required elements, such as the project logo, and the EU logo and disclaimer.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Figure 6 SeaClear2.0 Oral presentation poster template

3.4 Project Poster

A project poster has been developed, according to the guidelines provided by the European Commission and following the style proposed by the EC poster development tool (Figure 7). The poster is in A3 size. According to the requirements stemming from Article 50 of Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 of the European Parliament and the Council of 24 June 2021 (Common Provisions Regulation, CPR), beneficiaries and bodies implementing financial instruments must “publicly displaying at a location clearly visible to the public at least one poster of a minimum size A3 or equivalent electronic display with information about the operation highlighting the support from the Funds”.³

³ European Union (2022). Support kit for EU visibility. 2021-2027 brand book for managing authorities and project beneficiaries.
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/policy/communication/support_kit_visibility_2127_en.pdf

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Figure 7 SeaClear2.0 Project Poster

3.5 Project Roll-up Banner

A project roll-up banner has been developed (Figure 8). This is intended to be printed and displayed at meetings and events. The roll-up banner presents key information about the project, including its key activities, the consortium and the project website, and clearly acknowledges EU funding.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

Scalable, full-cycle marine litter remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and participatory solutions

Our Approach

- **Autonomous robotic system for seabed and floating litter collection**
- **Collected litter analysis and solutions for valorization**
- **Community activation and engagement**
- **Participatory practices for marine litter prevention**
- **Recommendations for effective policy making**
- **Scalability and replicability through Cascade Funding**

Partnership

Follow us!
www.seaclear2.eu

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 8 SeaClear2.0 Project Roll-up Banner

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

4. Communication Tools

A project website, social media accounts, an introductory project presentation, and an animation video have been/are being developed to help communicate information, events/activities and results about the project. These are presented below.

4.1 Project Website

The project website (www.seaclear2.eu) is a key tool for promoting the project and disseminating the project's results to a wide audience. The website is compliant with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation of the EU (privacy statement and cookie bar). Google analytics has been set up for the website, to monitor traffic and use.

The website will remain active throughout the duration of the project, and for at least 4 years after the project's completion. Over the duration of the project the website will be continuously updated to provide news and information about events/activities, and act as a repository for public project deliverables and other outputs.

The website is responsive, allowing easy viewing on all devices, and its structure is easy and intuitive. The top menu includes links to the following pages: Home, About, Results, News and Events. Additional ones, e.g. for Media, will be added as the project progresses if it is deemed necessary. The project footer, which is the same on all pages, includes the EU logo, project funding statement and the disclaimer, as well as links to the project's social media accounts, and a button to sign up to the project newsletter.

The SeaClear2.0 website is a 'live' communication tool that will be updated and revised as the project progresses to ensure that it optimally communicates and disseminates information about the project.

4.2 Social Media Channels

The SeaClear2.0 project will build on the results and outputs of project SeaClear (Grant Agreement No. 871295), both in terms of technological innovation and in terms of public outreach and stakeholder engagement. It therefore makes sense to maintain and continue to update and build on the social media channels developed by the SeaClear project, rather than abandon them and develop new ones for SeaClear2.0. Therefore, following approval by the European Commission, SeaClear2.0 has 'adopted' the social media channels of the SeaClear project. In essence, this means that SeaClear and SeaClear2.0 social media channels will be merged for the one year of overlap between the projects, with SeaClear2.0 maintaining them and further developing them for the remainder of its duration. This approach offers the following advantages:

1. It maximises the reach of both projects, as the new members of the SeaClear2.0 consortium and the community-centred SeaClear2.0 activities will attract new followers;
2. It highlights the continuity between the two projects and the importance of this in European research;
3. It contributes to the sustainability of both projects.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

SeaClear2.0 communicates its activities, events and updates through the following social media channels:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/SeaClear1and2>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/seaclearproject>
- Instagram: <https://bit.ly/3oKbZa4>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/seaclear-project>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/seaclearproject>

The project’s social media channels are regularly updated and monitored. As they are shared between SeaClear and SeaClear2.0, a joint logo has been developed (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Joint SeaClear and SeaClear2.0 logo for use on social media channels

4.3 SeaClear2.0 Zenodo Community

A SeaClear2.0 project community has been set up on Zenodo, available through this link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/seaclear2/>. Zenodo is an open science data repository developed by CERN that is fully compliant and linked with the European Commission’s OpenAIRE. It allows self-archiving and data storage of any files, in any format. The SeaClear2.0 community has been developed to facilitate the sharing of publicly available data and information about the project, such as for example conference posters and presentations, press releases, etc, as well as to self-archive research papers (by defining embargo periods etc.).

4.4 SeaClear2.0 Introductory Presentation

A presentation describing the aims and objectives of the SeaClear2.0 project and briefly presenting its main activities has been developed and shared with the partnership. It can be used to present the project at relevant meetings and events, and partners are free to adapt it to the specific needs/topics of each meeting/event. The presentation is available on the project’s shared drive and has also been uploaded to the project’s Zenodo community, accessible via this link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7861730>.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

4.5 Animation Video

An animation video describing the SeaClear2.0 system is being developed, as an additional communication tool. It will have a duration of maximum one minute and will be an important communication and engagement tool shared through the project’s social media channels. The video is expected to be ready by M9.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

5. Communication and Dissemination Guidelines

This chapter is a brief Communication and Dissemination Guide for the SeaClear2.0 project partnership. Active online presence is key for keeping audiences engaged, expanding the project’s audience base, and promoting the work within the framework of the SeaClear2.0 project. Project visibility is a collaborative task coming together through the contribution of all project partners. Almost all partners have time allocated in WP6 and are therefore expected to contribute to the project’s communication and dissemination activities. Some easy ways to do so:

- Write a short news article for our website/press and media.
- Send ISOTECH any relevant articles, events, news, etc. you might come across.
- Share with ISOTECH any project news, updates, activities.
- Let ISOTECH know about your upcoming project plans.

Please share your communication/dissemination material and any questions that you might have with network@isotech.com.cy.

Below are some quick guidelines regarding the communication and dissemination activities.

5.1 Project Information on Institutional Websites and Social Media

All partners are required to provide a short description of the project on their official website, if such site is available, and on their social media accounts (i.e. through a post about the project). The description should include the project aims and results and highlight the financial support of the European Union.

5.2 Project Poster Display

All partners are required to display a physical or electronic copy of the project poster on their premises, in such a way so that it is fully visible by the public.

5.3 Acknowledgement of EU Funding

EU funding must be acknowledged on all communication and dissemination material, and failure to do so could have budgetary repercussions. EU funding must be acknowledged through the EU emblem followed by a specific statement, which can be adapted depending on the type of communication/dissemination material.

5.3.1 EU emblem

The EU Flag is the most important visual brand used to acknowledge EU funding for projects. The EU flag should be used as appears below.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

The EU emblem can be downloaded from the EC's download centre: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

The colours, stars, or proportions of the EU emblem cannot be distorted. Detailed rules for the correct use of the EU emblem are available here: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

5.3.2 **Funding and Disclaimer Statement**

All project publications (e.g. reports, posters, deliverables, press releases etc.) should include the EU emblem together with the following statement (this is particularly important when opinions/views are expressed in the publications):

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

When materials with limited space are printed with project funds, the following EU logo and co-funding acknowledgement can be used:

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The EU logo download centre contains versions of these in several languages and formats (https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en)

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

5.4 Scientific Publications and Data

According to EC requirements, peer-reviewed scientific publications arising from Horizon Europe funded projects are to be made openly accessible, free of charge. This applies to:

- peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals) or
- research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

Partners can select between:

- 'green' open access (self-archiving): the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript needs to be deposited in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. The project community on Zenodo, or another suitable platform, can be used to this end.
- 'gold' open access: an article is immediately published in open access mode. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers to the article authors. Gold open access publication costs are eligible costs in Horizon Europe grants.

More information about the procedure for the publication of scientific articles and data, including the rules on giving prior notice to project partners are available in D1.1 Project Handbook and the SeaClear2.0 Consortium Agreement.

5.5 Press Articles

Press articles are a great way to share information about the project, and they can be used to reach specific target audiences e.g. through articles in industry magazines etc. Below are some quick guidelines for developing them:

- Ensure you are saying something that is of interest and relevant to the target audience
- Keep it short – maximum 500 words
- Avoid jargon and scientific terminology (unless you are targeting a scientific audience)
- Include photo and video material whenever possible (recommended min. 2 images in high resolution, JPG or PNG format)
- Include the EU funding acknowledgment and disclaimer
- Include link to project website
- Add a short paragraph at the end for the editor. This should include:
 - Key information about the project
 - Contact information for further details
 - The project website and social media handles

For any questions or assistance, contact: network@isotech.com.cy.

5.6 Social Media Posts

ISOTECH is managing the project's social media channels, as described above. All partners are encouraged to:

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

- Like and follow SeaClear2.0’s social media pages and urge their institutional page’s follower-base to do the same
- Reshare news from their institutional social media pages to SeaClear2.0’s social media pages and vice-versa
- Post news about the SeaClear2.0 project on their institutional social media pages and tag SeaClear2.0. When doing so, partners are also encouraged to:
 - Keep messages short - max. 50 words or 2 short paragraphs (for Facebook and Instagram)
 - Include project funding acknowledgement (please see above) in all posts
 - Use project hashtag (#SeaClear2) and any other popular hashtags relevant to your post – max. 3 hashtags. Possible suggestions include: #EUmission, #HorizonEU, #OceanEU #OceanMission, #Oceans, #maritime
 - Use relevant emojis – max. 3 emojis
 - Include photo and video material whenever possible (recommended – min. 1 image in high res., JPG or PNG format). Partners can also use free stock photos from online resources, such as [Unsplash](https://unsplash.com).

5.7 Continuous Reporting of Communication and Dissemination Activities

A log for reporting all publications and other communication and dissemination activities has been developed and shared with all partners. Partners are required to update this log regularly. To minimise time and effort, we would recommend updating the Log once a week or record any new communication activities right after they happen to ensure nothing falls through the cracks, but also to contribute towards more swift and efficient reporting processes.

For the link to the log please contact network@isotech.com.cy.

 101093822	D6.2: Dissemination Resources	
	WP6: Public Engagement, Policy, Dissemination	Version: V1.1
	Author(s): D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH Ltd), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH Ltd)	Level: PU

6. Conclusions

The information presented herein aim to help the SeaClear2.0 partnership establish a strong visual identify for the project, and implement engaging and impactful communication and dissemination activities, along the strategy and plan set in project Deliverable 6.1. The templates, tools and resources presented in this report will be updated as necessary over the duration of the project, to ensure that they remain relevant and effective.